

Self-referenced integrated plasmato-photonic sensor for temperature compensated refractive index sensing measurements

S. Simos^{1*}, L. Damakoudi¹, E. Chatzianagnostou¹, K. Fotiadis¹, D. Spasopoulos¹,
D. V. Bellas^{1,2}, O. Bhalerao^{3,4}, S. Suckow³, M. C. Lemme^{3,4} and N. Pleros¹

¹Department of Informatics - CIRI, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

²Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Ioannina, Ioannina, 45110, Greece

³AMO GmbH, Advanced Microelectronic Center Aachen (AMICA), Otto-Blumenthal-Strasse, Aachen, Germany

⁴RWTH Aachen University, Chair of Electronic Devices, Otto-Blumenthal-StraÙe 25, 52074 Aachen

*corresponding author: simostyl@csd.auth.gr

Abstract: In this work we propose a self-referenced plasmato-photonic refractive index sensor configuration, integrated on a polymer platform, to compensate for the effect of temperature.

Integrated plasmato-photonic sensors leverage the enhanced sensing credentials of plasmonics with the low-loss characteristics of photonics paving the way for powerful sensing devices with small footprint. On top of that, when integrated in polymer-based photonic platforms, they can offer lower-cost and faster fabrication [1,2]. However, due to the high thermo-optic coefficient of polymeric materials, temperature-induced variations become more prominent and limit the sensor performance. To date, several works have reported methods to compensate the effect of temperature on optical refractive index (RI) sensing. However, most of them consider fiber-based sensors while the respective works on integrated photonic circuits are limited to Si-based platforms [3,4], leaving room for further investigation on polymeric integrated devices.

In this work, we propose an integrated self-referenced scheme to compensate for the effect of temperature variations and improve the performance of the Aluminum-on-SU-8 bimodal plasmato-photonic sensor reported in [1]. The proposed self-referenced sensor is realized by cascading an SU-8 Bragg grating after the bimodal interferometer, as illustrated in the 3D schematic representation of Fig. 1(a). The bimodal sensor consists of an Aluminum stripe with 75 μm length located between two access SU-8 waveguides and on top of a thinner SU-8 layer. The working principle and the experimental evaluation of the sensor have been shown in detail in [1,5]. The Bragg grating has been placed at the bimodal sensor output to serve as a reference by tracking temperature variations. Opting for a narrow Bragg grating resonance at the edge of the sensor spectral response, a period of 520 nm and waveguide widths of $W_1 = 7 \mu\text{m}$ and $W_2 = 6.1 \mu\text{m}$ have been selected after numerical simulations.

Fig. 1. (a) 3D schematic layout of the self-referenced bimodal plasmato-photonic sensor. (b) Spectral responses at constant temperature when mediums with different RIs are applied on the sensor surface.

The spectral response of the proposed configuration consists of two parts: (i) the sensor spectral response

comprising wavelength dips due to the bimodal interference and (ii) a sharp wavelength dip due to the Bragg grating resonance, as can be seen in Fig. 1(b). The simulated spectral responses of the proposed configuration when mediums with different RIs are applied on the sensor surface at a constant temperature are illustrated in Fig. 1(b). As can be observed, the RI changes cause a wavelength shift to the bimodal dips ($\Delta\lambda_{RI}^{Bimodal}$) revealing a sensitivity of 6078 nm/RIU, which is close to the experimentally reported values of [5], while the Bragg grating resonance remains unaffected by these changes due to being covered with cladding ($\Delta\lambda_{RI}^{Bragg} = 0$) making it ideal for a reference structure. Fig. 2(a) shows the respective simulated spectral response when the configuration is exposed to different temperatures and considering that a material with the same RI is applied on top of its surface. As can be observed, both parts of the transfer function are affected by variations in temperature with the bimodal sensor and the Bragg exhibiting a temperature sensitivity of 687 pm/K and 111pm/K, respectively. From these results, we can extract the calibration curve of the proposed self-referenced sensor shown in Fig. 2(b) which correlates the thermal shift of the bimodal dip ($\Delta\lambda_{\Delta T}^{Bimodal}$) with the thermal shift of the Bragg resonance ($\Delta\lambda_{\Delta T}^{Bragg}$) cancelling the factor of temperature.

Fig. 2. (a) Spectral responses and resonances shifting for different temperatures. (b) Calibration curve. (c) Spectral responses and resonances drifting for different RIs and different temperatures. (d) Magnified view of the Bragg resonance drift.

Figure 2(c) shows a practical example of how the bimodal dips are shifted when both RI and temperature changes occur, while Fig. 2(d) presents a zoomed in view of the Bragg resonance shifts that are affected only by temperature. Measuring this $\Delta\lambda_{\Delta T}^{Bragg}$ and using the calibration curve of Fig. 2(b), we can define the shift of the bimodal dip due to the temperature change and subtract it from the total shift. For example, the $\Delta\lambda_{Total}^{Bimodal}$ corresponding to the black and blue curves of Fig. 2(c) is 40.21 nm, while the $\Delta\lambda_{\Delta T}^{Bragg}$ equals to 2.3 nm corresponding to the $\Delta\lambda_{\Delta T}^{Bimodal}$ value of 13.98 nm according to the calibration curve. By subtracting this value from the $\Delta\lambda_{Total}^{Bimodal}$, we find that the pure $\Delta\lambda_{RI}^{Bimodal}$ equals to 26.23 nm which is in good agreement with the value of 26.7 nm calculated from Fig. 1(b).

Therefore, the proposed polymer-based self-referenced sensor can effectively compensate for the temperature-induced wavelength drift hence eliminating a major flaw of polymer sensing platforms enhancing their resolution.

This work was supported by European H2020 projects ICT GRACED (no. 101007448) and AMBROSIA (no. 101093166).

References

1. K. Fotiadis et al., ACS Photonics (2023), doi:10.1021/acsp Photonics.3c00290
2. L. Ji et al., Photonic Sensors (2020), doi:10.1007/s13320-020-0589-y
3. J. Li et al., Optik (2021), doi:10.1016/j.ijleo.2021.166838
4. K. B. Gylfason et al., Optics Express (2010), doi:10.1364/oe.18.003226
5. K. Fotiadis et al., "Single-arm Interferometric Plasmonic Sensor integrated on a cladded polymeric photonic platform" CLEO 2024 (accepted)